

Room-temperature continuous-wave perovskite polariton lasers

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Despite the decades of research, the performance of solution-processed lasers remains inferior to that of III-V semiconductor lasers. The benefit of low-cost fabrication comes at the expense of higher lasing thresholds, limited by the performance-cost trade-offs in solution-processed semiconductors. Here we demonstrate room-temperature, continuous-wave perovskite polariton lasers with remarkably low thresholds of $\sim 0.4 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, enabled by high-quality and tunable single-crystal perovskite microcavities. The thresholds are an order of magnitude (~ 30 times) lower than those of state-of-the-art III-V semiconductor lasers under optical pumping, and are record-low for solution-processed lasers. The ultralow-threshold lasing arises from exciton-polariton condensation, a macroscopic coherent quantum state akin to Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC) operating in steady-state, a condition achieved for the first time for solution-processed semiconductors. The BEC-like state is attained by fine-tuning the cavity photon-exciton energy separation near the degeneracy point for strong light-matter interactions. These mechanisms allow us to realise an indirectly injected perovskite laser chip powered by a GaN LED. Our findings create exciting avenues toward on-chip integration of solution-processed lasers, and a new room-temperature, quasi-equilibrium playground for polariton BECs.

Solution-processed semiconductor lasers, including those based on organic¹⁻⁵, colloidal quantum-dot⁶⁻⁹ and halide perovskite¹⁰⁻¹⁴ materials, show strong promises as a new generation of coherent light sources for large-area, flexible and integrated photonics. Amongst the lasing materials, halide perovskites have been identified as an exceptional class¹⁰⁻¹⁶, they exhibit a range of desirable properties including strong optical gain, high emission quantum yields, tunable wavelengths, and the ease of preparation, as were similarly found in other optoelectronic applications¹⁷⁻²². In 2020, room-temperature continuous-wave (CW) lasing from perovskites was demonstrated¹², showing low thresholds of $\sim 45 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$.

Despite the encouraging advances, the performance of perovskite lasers (or solution-processed lasers in general) is typically inferior to that of the best III-V semiconductor lasers, which show thresholds of down to $\sim 12 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ under optical pumping²³. Further development in this direction is limited by the trade-off between quality and processing simplicity of solution-processed semiconductors.

In this work, we demonstrate the first CW perovskite polariton laser, achieving a remarkably low lasing threshold of $\sim 0.4 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ at room temperature. The laser construction consists of a high-quality perovskite

single crystal (SC) contained within a finely tunable Fabry-Perot micro-resonator (Fig. 1a). The lasing thresholds are more than one order of magnitude lower than those achieved in state-of-the-art III-V semiconductor lasers under optical pumping²³⁻²⁵, setting a new record for the threshold of solution-processed lasers.

Beyond our experiments that rigorously demonstrate the key attributes of lasing²⁶, we find that the record-low threshold originates from exciton-polariton condensation²⁷⁻³⁴, a macroscopic coherent quantum state resembling a Bose-Einstein condensate (BEC)^{27, 29, 35} operating in the steady-state; this is a condition not achieved before for solution-processed semiconductors. The BEC-like state is obtained through an optimum cavity photon-exciton energy separation near the degeneracy point, allowing the strong coupling of light and matter in the perovskite single-crystal microcavity. The polariton condensation is found to dramatically reduce the lasing threshold by two orders of magnitude compared to that of conventional photon lasing for the same gain medium. The extremely low threshold leads to the realization of an indirectly injected perovskite laser chip driven by a GaN LED.

Fabrication and material characterization of the CW perovskite polariton lasers

The microcavity used in this work consists of a mixed-cation lead bromide perovskite single crystal sandwiched between two distributed Bragg reflectors (DBRs) with alternating layers of SiO₂/TiO₂ (Fig. 1a&b). The perovskite single crystals were prepared using a space-confined inverse-temperature crystallisation method³⁶⁻³⁹ (Fig. 1c). An array of Au pillars (diameter: 1 μm) were thermally evaporated onto a DBR, followed by the placement of another DBR. The Au pillars act as a spacer between the two DBRs, forming empty channels for single crystal growth. The precursor solution was introduced into the channels, followed by annealing at 80°C to form the single crystals. The thickness of the perovskite single crystals (and the cavity lengths) could be freely tuned between 0.1–1.5 μm (Extended Data Fig. 1) by adjusting the height of the evaporated Au pillars.

Halide perovskites with mixed A-site cations were reported to demonstrate superior optoelectronic properties and stability⁴⁰. We find that, by introducing formamidinium (FA) into the perovskite composition (to form FA_xMA_{1-x}PbBr₃), employing mixed solvents of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylformamide (DMF), and introducing a hydrophobic polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) layer (between the perovskite and the bottom DBR), it is possible to obtain perovskite single crystals with further refined quality (Extended Data Fig. 2). From our nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) results, the molar ratios of FA⁺ to MA⁺ in the precursor solution are found to closely agree with the actual stoichiometric ratios of the corresponding cations in the perovskite single crystals (Supplementary Fig. 1). The optimised FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystals show a low trap density of $\sim 8.7 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (four orders of magnitude lower than that of polycrystalline FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ films, Extended Data Fig. 3), a long PL lifetime of >400 ns (Fig. 1d), and a high external photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) of $\sim 33.4\%$ (Fig. 1e).

Fig. 1 | Fabrication and material characterization of the perovskite polariton lasers. **a**, Schematic representation of a CW perovskite polariton laser. A perovskite single crystal is sandwiched between a pair of highly reflective DBRs, supporting CW lasing action through strong light-matter interactions. **b**, Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) images of the DBR, showing bilayers of SiO₂ (blue regions) and TiO₂ (green regions). **c**, Fabrication processes of the single-crystal perovskite microcavities. **d**, Transient PL decay curves of perovskite samples (excitation wavelength: 400 nm; fluence: 42 nJ cm⁻²). FMPB denotes FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ perovskite. SC denotes single-crystal samples. PC denotes polycrystalline samples. **e**, PLQY as a function of excitation intensity for various perovskite samples. **f**, Absorption and PL spectra of a FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystal (thickness: ~ 200 nm). **g**, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystal. **h**, Fluorescent microscope image of a FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ perovskite single crystal. **i**, XRD patterns of FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystal and polycrystalline samples.

The optical absorption and PL of the FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystals show small Stokes shift and significant spectral overlap (Fig. 1f). The absorption curves can be modelled using the Elliott formula (see Supplementary Note 1 and Supplementary Fig. 2)⁴¹, revealing an exciton binding energy of ~41 meV and an exciton peak position of ~2.32 eV. The exciton binding energy is slightly larger than the thermal

energy at room temperature (26 meV). In this case, correlated and uncorrelated e–h pairs (i.e., excitons and free carriers) are expected to coexist in thermal equilibrium under excitation intensities near which polariton lasing can occur (10^{15} - 10^{18} cm⁻³), according to the Saha equation (see Supplementary Note 2 and Supplementary Fig. 3)¹⁵. The FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystals exhibit uniform surface morphology free from macroscopic dislocations (Fig. 1g), showing an RMS roughness of ~0.6 nm (Extended Data Fig. 2), allowing minimum optical scattering losses as an active medium for polariton lasing. In contrast, a higher surface roughness (RMS) of ~6.8 nm is observed for polycrystalline samples. The FA_{0.1}MA_{0.9}PbBr₃ single crystals show bright and uniform photoluminescence (PL) under UV illumination (Fig. 1h). In addition, the single-crystal samples show sharper and fewer X-ray diffraction (XRD) peaks compared to those of polycrystalline films with a similar composition (Fig. 1i), consistent with the higher crystallinity of the single crystals.

Demonstration of CW lasing from polariton condensation

To characterize the lasing properties, the single-crystal perovskite microcavities were pumped off resonance using a 405-nm CW diode laser. As the excitation intensity increases to above ~0.4 W cm⁻², the emission peak at ~551 nm rises sharply (Fig. 2a). The real-space images of the emission beam (Extended Data Fig. 4) show a transition from weak diffuse luminescence to intense directional emission. The emission intensity as a function of excitation intensity is plotted on a log–log scale (Fig. 2b), showing a threshold (P_{th}) of 0.4 W cm⁻². The emission intensity from the microcavity increases sub-linearly below the threshold; this may be attributed to self-reabsorption losses inside the cavity⁴². The increase becomes super-linear and quadratic above the threshold. In the regime closer to saturation, the increase of emission intensity becomes linear. Narrowing of linewidth from ~1.3 nm to ~0.54 nm across the threshold is observed (Fig. 2b), accompanied by a blueshift (~1.5 nm) of the emission peak. The emission spectra gradually broaden under higher pump intensities, likely owing to the fluctuation of polariton population and saturation of occupied ground states. The temporal coherence properties of the emission from the microcavities were examined using a Michelson interferometer. The first-order coherence function $g^1(\tau)$ (Fig. 2c) is given by the visibility of the interference fringes. At zero time-delay ($\tau = 0$ ps) above the threshold, the collected interference pattern shows a maximum fringe visibility contrast of 69% (Fig. 2c, inset). The clear threshold (Fig. 2b), linewidth narrowing (Fig. 2b), beam profiles (Extended Data Fig. 4), polarisation of emission (Extended Data Fig. 5), as well as temporal coherence (Fig 2c and Extended Data Fig. 6) are consistent with the characters of lasing according to well-established measurement protocols²⁶. The perovskite lasers show decent operational lifetimes (T_{50}) of ~6.4 hours under continuous pumping with an intensity of 0.9 W cm⁻² (Extended Data Fig. 7).

Fig. 2 | CW polariton lasing from single-crystal perovskite microcavities at room temperature. **a**, Evolution of emission spectra under CW operation at different pump intensities. Single-crystal sample thickness: ~ 120 nm. **b**, Light-output intensity, FWHM and emission blueshift as functions of CW pump intensity (at ~ 300 K). **c**, Temporal coherence of the CW polariton laser. The first-order coherence $g^1(\tau)$ above the threshold, measured using a Michelson interferometer. The red solid line represents a Gaussian fit to the data. The inset shows the Michelson interference pattern at zero time delay. Scale bar: $5 \mu\text{m}$. **d**, The angle-resolved PL spectra above the lasing threshold ($3.0P_{\text{th}}$). The straight line represents the dispersion relation of excitons. The solid parabolic curve represents the dispersion relation of cavity photons. The dashed curve represents the dispersion of the lower polariton branch. Above the lasing threshold, the polaritons are found to condense at the bottom of the LP branch. **e**, Polariton occupancy in the ground- and excited-states, plotted in a semi-logarithmic scale for pump intensities below ($0.8P_{\text{th}}$), around ($\sim 1.0P_{\text{th}}$), and above ($3.0P_{\text{th}}$) the threshold (at ~ 300 K). For each pump intensity, the zero of the energy scale corresponds to the energy of the $k_{\parallel} = 0$ ground state, the horizontal axis shows the energy shift from the energy at $k_{\parallel} = 0$. We assign the ground-state occupancy to be one at threshold. The blue dashed line represents the Maxwell–Boltzmann distribution function with $k_{\text{B}}T = 26$ meV, showing good agreement with the on-threshold polariton occupancy. **f**, Comparison of CW lasing thresholds for lasers based on different classes of semiconductor materials. See Supplementary Table 1 for details. S1-S26 are the numbers of supplementary references. **g**, Schematic illustration of an indirectly injected perovskite laser chip, powered by a 450-nm GaN LED ($P_{\text{max}} = 3$ W). **h**, Emission intensity and FWHM of the perovskite polariton laser chip as functions of driving current in the GaN LED (DC, at ~ 300 K). **i**, Polariton lasing spectra from microcavities of different lengths (adjusted

using the single-crystal thickness). Tunable lasing wavelength from 545 nm to 557 nm was achieved at a driving current of 60 mA.

The occurrence of steady-state polariton condensation responsible for the ultralow-threshold lasing can be observed through angle-resolved emission measurements at room temperature (see Fig. 2d for above-threshold condition, and Extended Data Fig. 8 for below- and near-threshold conditions). The solid curves in Fig. 2d are the dispersion relations of the uncoupled exciton ($E_{\text{ex}} = 2.32$ eV) and cavity photon modes ($E_{\text{cav}}(\theta) = E_{\text{cav}}(0)(1 - \sin^2\theta/n_{\text{eff}}^2)^{-1/2}$, where θ is the emission angle and n_{eff} is the effective refractive index). The dashed curve shows the dispersion relation of the lower polariton (LP) branch from the coupled harmonic oscillator mode^{27, 43}, which can be described by $E_{\text{LP}} = \frac{(E_{\text{cav}} + E_{\text{ex}}) - \sqrt{(E_{\text{cav}} - E_{\text{ex}})^2 + (\hbar\Omega)^2}}{2}$, where $\hbar\Omega$ is the Rabi splitting energy that is found to be ~ 115 meV (See Supplementary Note 3 and Supplementary Fig. 4). The ground state near the minimum of the LP dispersion ($E_{\text{LP}}(k_{\parallel}=0) = 2.251$ eV, where k_{\parallel} is the in-plane wavevector) becomes massively occupied, in clear contrast to conventional photon lasing in which an occupation of the minimum of the cavity-mode dispersion curve ($E_{\text{cav}}(k_{\parallel}=0) = 2.292$ eV) is expected. The enhanced ground-state occupation at the bottom of the polariton dispersion relation is a defining feature of polariton condensation^{14, 30}. In contrast, for a weakly coupled perovskite microcavity with poorer optical quality (Supplementary Fig. 5), only cavity modes are seen in the angle-resolved emission spectra (Extended Data Fig. 9) without any evidence for lasing.

The occupancy of polaritons as a function of their energy (relative to the ground state) at different pump intensities is shown in Fig. 2e. At very low excitation intensities, the polariton occupancy is not thermalized²⁷. At the lasing threshold, the occupancy function can be modelled using a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: $n(E)/\exp(-\Delta E/k_{\text{B}}T)$, where $\Delta E = E_{k_{\parallel}} - E_{k_{\parallel}=0}$ and k_{B} is Boltzmann's constant, indicating thermal equilibrium of polaritons at room temperature^{27, 29}. Above the threshold, a peak in the energetic distribution near $k_{\parallel}=0$ can be observed, consistent with the formation of polariton condensation near the ground-state of the LP dispersion^{14, 30}.

Together, the blueshift of emission wavelengths (Fig. 2b), narrowing of the emission spectra in the energy and momentum spaces (Fig. 2b and Extended Data Fig. 8), and the excitation-dependent occupancy functions (Fig. 2e) indicate that the low-threshold CW lasing arises from steady-state polariton condensation, a coherent quantum state similar to the BEC^{29, 32}.

Record-low threshold and an indirectly injected perovskite laser chip

Remarkably, the threshold of 0.4 W cm^{-2} for the CW perovskite polariton lasers is significantly lower than those of the state-of-the-art inorganic semiconductor lasers based on III-V, II-VI and oxide materials under optical pumping, and are record-low for solution-processed lasers based on organic, colloidal quantum dot (CQD), and perovskite semiconductors (Fig. 2f and Supplementary Table 1). The perovskite polariton lasers are highly reproducible, showing an average CW lasing threshold of 0.76 W cm^{-2} and a standard deviation of 0.19 W cm^{-2} (Supplementary Fig. 6).

The ultralow-threshold polariton lasing allowed us to demonstrate the first indirectly injected perovskite laser chip (PeLC). The PeLC was constructed using the single-crystal perovskite microcavity directly attached to a GaN LED (peak wavelength: 450 nm; maximum power: 3 W; driven by DC current) (Fig. 2g). A drastic increase of the output intensity from the microcavity was observed for driving currents of above ~ 41 mA, accompanied by a clear linewidth narrowing from ~ 1.6 nm to ~ 0.8 nm across the threshold (Fig. 2h). The lengths of the microcavities could be tuned by varying the perovskite single crystal thickness. Single-mode lasing with tunable wavelengths from 545 nm to 557 nm was achieved (Fig. 2i). The fact that CW lasing can be achieved with an indirectly injected configuration⁴⁴ under low DC currents of ~ 41 mA (~ 4.1 A cm⁻²) indicate the exceptional potential of perovskite polariton lasers as on-chip photon sources.

The transition from polariton to photon lasing

Beyond the aforementioned steady-state (CW pumped) experiments, we extend our investigations into the pulsed mode (using a fs laser) where excitation intensities exceeding the damage threshold of CW operation (~ 400 W cm⁻²) can be accessed. This allows us to observe the transition from polariton to photon lasing using a series of pump fluences (Fig. 3a). Under pulsed excitation, the threshold of polariton lasing (P_{th1}) is about 0.3 $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, which is about two orders of magnitude smaller than the threshold of photon lasing ($P_{th2} = 12.4$ $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$). Similar to what observed for CW operation, the non-linear rise of output intensity is accompanied by a blueshift of peak wavelengths and linewidth narrowing (Fig. 3b and Supplementary Fig. 7). The linewidth of the polariton emission reduces across the threshold; it broadens again as the pump fluence further increases. A blueshift of emission (~ 1.3 nm) relative to the minimum of the LP branch, a signature of polariton lasing, is observed. These phenomena could be attributed to polariton-polariton interactions⁴⁵. As the pump fluence further increases, the emission energy exhibits another significant blueshift toward the minimum of the cavity-mode dispersion relation (2.273 eV). The second region of linewidth narrowing near $P_{th2} = 12.4$ $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ is also observed. Amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) of the perovskite single crystals (without DBR cavities) is observed at pump fluences of above 57.6 $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ (Supplementary Fig. 8), which is 3.6 times higher than the threshold of photon lasing for the same gain medium.

Fig. 3 | Polariton to photon lasing transition in single-crystal perovskite microcavities. **a**, Emission intensity (I)-pump fluence (I_0) curve of a single-crystal perovskite microcavity, showing two thresholds at pump fluence of $0.3 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ and $12.4 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ corresponding to polariton lasing and photon lasing, respectively. The samples were pumped using a 400-nm fs laser (pulse width: 270 fs, repetition rate: 50 kHz, single-crystal thickness: ~ 130 nm). Above the first threshold, the increase in output intensity is super-linear with a power-law dependence of $I \propto I_0^{2.36}$. In the regime where photon lasing (light amplification by stimulated emission) occurs, the intensity increases more sharply with $I \propto I_0^{6.67}$. **b**, FWHM and wavelength blueshift as functions of pump fluence, showing dramatic changes at the two thresholds. The shaded areas are regions near the thresholds. **c**, Spectra of spontaneous emission, polariton lasing and photon lasing from the single-crystal perovskite. **d**, The polarisation characteristics. **e**, Temporal second-order coherence $g^2(0)$ of polariton lasing and photon lasing. The grey-shaded area shows the photon lasing regime. **f-i**, Angle-resolved emission spectra of a single-crystal perovskite microcavity at different pump fluence; (f) $P = 0.8P_{th1}$, (g) $P = 2P_{th1}$, (h) $P \sim P_{th2}$, (i) $P = 1.6P_{th2}$.

The spontaneous emission, polariton lasing and photon lasing from the perovskite single crystals show distinctively different spectra (Fig. 3c). The spontaneous emission from a bare perovskite single crystal is centred at ~ 2.305 eV with a FWHM of ~ 18 nm. When assembled into a microcavity, under low to medium excitation intensities (0.1 - $10 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) the emission of ground-state polariton is located at ~ 2.258 eV with

a narrowing of linewidth to ~ 0.8 nm, corresponding to a quality factor (Q) of ~ 688 . When the pump fluence exceeds the threshold of photon lasing, the emission FWHM continues to reduce to ~ 0.5 nm ($Q \approx 1092$). The emission peak blueshifts to 2.273 eV at the same time.

Further, we compare the polarisation properties of the spontaneous emission, polariton lasing and photon lasing (Fig. 3d). Below the polariton lasing threshold (P_{th1}), the spontaneous emission is completely unpolarised. Above P_{th1} , the high density of polaritons arising from the strong coupling of cavity photons and excitons create a BEC-like polariton condensation with macroscopic coherence³⁰. The light emitting from the microcavity shows a degree of linear polarisation of $(I_{max} - I_{min})/(I_{max} + I_{min}) \approx 42.9\%$ (I_{max} is the maximum intensity at 0° , and I_{min} is the minimum intensity at 90°). As the pump fluence increases to above the photon lasing threshold (P_{th2}), a higher degree of linear polarisation ($\sim 81.8\%$) is achieved. We note that the polariton lasing shows a smaller degree of polarisation compared to that of photon lasing, consistent with that reported for polariton lasing from III-V and organic semiconductors^{46,47}. The variation of the second-order coherence $g^2(0)$ with the normalized pump intensity P/P_{th1} ($P_{th1} = 0.3 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) is shown in Fig. 3e and Extended Data Fig. 10. A rapid transition from a thermal to a coherent state is found. Near P_{th1} , where the ground-state occupation number (\tilde{n}) is small, photon bunching is observed with a measured $g^2(0)$ of as high as 1.22. With the onset of quantum degeneracy and a sharp increase of \tilde{n} with the pump fluence, $g^2(0)$ quickly reduces to 1, resulting from a stronger coherence as the condensate forms. Further increasing the pump power to levels entering the photon lasing regime ($P > P_{th2}$), $g^2(0)$ remains to be ~ 1 , indicating the single-crystal perovskite microcavity is in coherent states during the transition from polariton to photon lasing.

Angle-resolved emission spectra of the single-crystal perovskite microcavities at different regimes of operation are presented in Fig. 3f-i. Below the polariton lasing threshold (P_{th1}), the polariton emission follows the profile of the LP dispersion over a wide range of angles (Fig. 3f). Under excitation intensities above P_{th1} , the polaritons condense into the ground-state, a much narrower energetic and angular distribution at the bottom of LP branch is observed (Fig. 3g). As the exciton density increases toward the Mott density, the Coulomb interactions required for stable excitons are weakened, creating an electron-hole plasma^{41, 48}. When the excitation fluence increases toward the second threshold (P_{th2}), a second emission peak corresponding to the cavity photon mode appears, indicating the simultaneous presence of cavity photon and polariton modes as the system transits from strong coupling to a weak coupling regime (Fig. 3h). Photon lasing occurs at above the second threshold (P_{th2}), with the energy and momentum of emission restricted to near the bottom of the cavity-mode dispersion relation (Fig. 3i). During the transition from polariton lasing to photon lasing, a clear blueshift of the emission peak from the bottom of the polariton branch to the cavity photon branch is observed (Fig. 3g-i).

The influence of detuning energy

We show below that detuning, the cavity photon-exciton energy separation ($\Delta = E_{cav} - E_{ex}$), is a key factor in enabling the ultralow threshold of polariton lasing from single-crystal perovskite microcavities. Using our method of perovskite single crystal growth (Methods), the cavity length and the cavity mode

position can be precisely controlled by the thickness of the single crystals, leading to finely adjustable detuning energies.

The angle-resolved emission spectra from the single-crystal perovskite microcavities with different detuning energies are shown in Fig 4a-c. At $\Delta = -54$ meV, the angular distribution of emission is relatively broad along the LP branch, indicating a considerable fraction of uncondensed polaritons. At $\Delta = -25$ and -12 meV, clear reductions in the energy and angular distributions toward the LP ground state are observed, consistent with the formation of polariton condensation. A similar finding could be observed in the energy-dependent occupancy of polaritons at different detuning energies (Fig. 4d). In the case of large detuning ($\Delta = -54$ meV), a polariton relaxation bottleneck is observed at excited states and polaritons tends to be resident at a broad range of energies⁴⁷. This may be related to inefficient polariton-polariton scattering processes for polaritons with a larger photon fraction, hindering polariton condensation⁴⁹. At smaller negative detuning ($\Delta = -40, -25$ and -12 meV), the increased excitonic component in polaritons leads to the more efficient relaxation of polaritons.

Fig. 4 | The effects of detuning energy on polariton lasing. a-c, Angle-resolved emission spectra of single-crystal perovskite microcavities for different detuning energies of (a) $\Delta = -54$, (b) $\Delta = -25$, and (c) $\Delta = -18$ meV (at $P = 3P_{\text{th}}$). The thicknesses of single-crystal samples in (a)-(c) are 100 nm, 120 nm and 140 nm, respectively. d, Polariton occupancy functions for different detuning energies (at $P = 3P_{\text{th}}$). e, The emission intensity-pump intensity characteristics for different detuning energies ($\Delta = -54, -40, -25, -12$ meV). f, Dependence of lasing threshold on detuning energy under pulsed (blue curve) and CW (red curve) pumping. CW polariton lasing is not observed for $\Delta < -62$ meV and $\Delta > -10$ meV.

The output intensity-pump fluence characteristics of the single-crystal perovskite microcavities are compared for different detuning energies (Fig. 4e). As the excitonic fraction increases (with less negative

Δ), the lasing threshold decreases from $\sim 8.8 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ at a detuning of -62 meV to 0.4 W cm^{-2} at a detuning of -28 meV under CW operation (a similar trend is observed under pulsed pumping) (Fig. 4f). However, further minimising the detuning energy leads to slightly increased thresholds, possibly due to the increased polariton effective mass arising from the higher fraction of excitons⁴⁷ and self-absorption losses⁵⁰. CW polariton lasing is not observed for $\Delta < -62 \text{ meV}$ and $\Delta > -10 \text{ meV}$, where the strong coupling between excitons and photons cannot be sustained. The analysis above exemplifies how detuning energies are optimised in the single-crystal perovskite microcavities for ultralow-threshold polariton lasing.

Conclusions

In summary, we have demonstrated the first CW perovskite polariton lasers, constructed using a high-quality mixed-cation perovskite single-crystal placed within a finely tunable Fabry-Perot microcavity. They show exceptionally low room-temperature CW lasing thresholds of $\sim 0.4 \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, which are an order of magnitude (~ 30 times) lower than those achieved in state-of-the-art III-V semiconductor lasers under optical pumping, setting a new record for solution-processed lasers (Fig. 2f and Supplementary Table 1). The clear threshold (Fig. 2b), linewidth narrowing (Fig. 2b), beam profiles (Extended Data Fig. 4), the polarisation of emission (Extended Data Fig. 5), and the temporal and spatial coherence (Fig 2c and Extended Data Fig. 6) clearly demonstrate the occurrence of lasing²⁶.

Additional characteristics of the perovskite microcavity, including blueshift of emission wavelengths (Fig. 2b), narrowing of the emission spectra in the energy and momentum spaces (Fig. 2d and Extended Data Fig. 8), the excitation-dependent occupancy functions (Fig. 2e), and the sub-Mott density carrier concentration (Supplementary Fig. 3) show that the record-low threshold arises from exciton-polariton condensation (Supplementary Note 4), a macroscopic coherent quantum state akin to a BEC^{29, 32} operating in the steady-state; this is a regime not formerly accessible for solution-processed semiconductors. Such ideal condition is established by adjusting the cavity photon-exciton energy separation near the degeneracy point, allowing strong light-matter interactions in the single-crystal microcavity. The polariton condensation reduces the lasing threshold by two orders of magnitude compared to that of conventional photon lasing for the same perovskite single crystals. These mechanisms lead to the realisation of the first indirectly injected perovskite laser chip (PeLC) powered by a GaN LED. We expect our findings to create exciting opportunities for the on-chip integration of solution-processed lasers for emerging applications, and a new room-temperature, quasi-equilibrium platform for polariton BECs.

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Author contributions

C.Z. and D.D. planned the study and designed the experiments. C.Z. fabricated and characterized the CW perovskite polariton lasers. X.C., Z.W. and Y.L. assisted in the fabrication processes. C.Z. carried out the spectroscopic and structural experiments and analyses with the assistance of X.C and Y.Y. C.Z. wrote the initial draft of the manuscript, which was revised by D.D. and B.Z. All authors contributed to the work and commented on the paper. D.D., C.Z. and B.Z. guided the project.

Competing interests

D.D., C.Z. and B.Z. are inventors on CN patent application No. 202311741014.4. The remaining authors declare no competing interests.

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